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Supporting rural creative firms is important for rural economies? – A call for place-based support

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Executive summary

This research highlights the critical importance of considering the needs and socio-spatial context of local artists/designers for providing place-based business support in rural areas. Tailored support to the specific rural conditions faced by designers/artists is essential for support effectiveness and long-term sustainability of creative offers. The research emphasizes the need for mobile offers from banks and business support services, as creatives cannot rely on consistent internet connectivity. Policy recommendations focus on leveraging existing private sector and Council communication channels and facilities to support local artists and designers, as this low-cost effort can have positive ripple effects for other local businesses.

Unlocking rural potential through supporting creative businesses for local socio-economic development

This research highlights the untapped potential of rural creative businesses, such as crafts, visual artists, photographers, sculpture artists, and furniture designers/makers. These passion-driven businesses, sometimes with a community focus, have a different balance between profit-making and realising a passion or unique skills set. They contribute, however, significantly to the local economy and well-being. Examples of impact include increasing educational creative opportunities with schools, communities via community centres, giving time to projects with vulnerable adults and children, attracting customers to an area through workshop offers and increasing the time visitors stay in a location, positively increasing tourist spending on hospitality and retail offers.

However, what is often overlooked, is this silent less visible socio-economic impact of these individuals and micro-businesses. This small impact could be increased and even scaled with relatively low-cost inputs from policymakers and civil servants in Parish and District Councils increasing local economic development. Initiatives could include:

- Mobile business services bridging the gap of missing business infrastructure.
- Leveraging existing infrastructure more effectively as location for temporary bank and business services.
- Scaling impact through more collaborations and network building support.

My research calls these mobile offers 'entrepreneurial places', as they materialise temporarily in known locations to service local businesses and help to manage money-flows. 'Place' is seen as a "(...) temporary localisation, consisting of the interplay of flows of money, visual impressions, verbal and bodily communication." (Hill et al., 2021, p. 645). By investing in rural creative businesses, we can create more vibrant and sustainable rural communities and economies.

Background

The new UK government recent industrial strategy '[Invest 2035](#)' (Department for Business and Trade, 2024) identifies the creative industries as vital growth sectors, underscoring their increasing significance (265K business in 2023, 9.7 % of all UK businesses). However, the rural locations of so many creative firms is not mentioned. Figure 1 showcases microclusters in England to illustrate rural locations of creative firms. The above strategy has an implicit urban focus, as most of the research findings are indeed based on urban-centric research.

Rural creatives and their unique locational challenges are frequently overlooked: typical infrastructure challenges affect rural areas distinctly: there are less customers and competitors due to lower density of population and firms; accessibility issues exist as many remote areas are underserved with public transport and delivery via postal services; most often, less business infrastructure – bank branches, business support services, training ([Hill and Mole, 2022](#)). Local suppliers and skilled professionals are often located many miles away in larger towns or cities, aggravating these conditions. Addressing these market failures, could contribute greatly to revitalising rural communities and economies.

Hence, this research's emphasis on 'place' is both timely and aligned with the UK [Creative industries section vision](#) by the Department for Digital, Culture, Media & Sport (DCMS, 2022), that highlights the importance of place-related policy. While the January 2025 announcement of the [£60 million investment into creative industries](#) as part of the upcoming UK Government's Sector Plan is commendable, the disproportionate location of funding beneficiaries in urban areas is concerning. This finding is particularly challenging, given that rural areas have similar clustering of creatives as urban ones (Velez-Ospina et al., 2023). Figure 1 illustrates the location of micro-

clusters of creative firms identified in rural England in 2019. Creative firms, often run as sole-traders, or single-director companies, in rural areas are often run from homes, with a possible garden shed as a studio, and often lack locations to exhibit their work and attract customers. While many areas in Cornwall and Devon, and in Scotland, have increased visibility for artists through small galleries in villages, central and Northwest England lag behind in this visibility.

The term 'life-style- business' is a company embedded into the local community, often supporting local issues and groups, and that is not solely prioritising profit making. The most important offers are delivered through their workshops, exhibitions and events, and education contributions. The benefits of these artists' engagements both for local communities and economies, do not only add cultural enrichment but also contribute to preservation of heritage skills, stress relief, overcoming loneliness, enhanced well-being, and local economic development through attracting more visitors to areas and increasing the lengths of stays in an area (Hill, 2021; Hill et al., 2024, Manning and Uygur, 2023). These benefits also contribute to increased local consumption in retail shops and hospitality firms, providing a boost to the local economy.

In this context, artists are seen as placemakers who facilitate the benefits above to emerge. Place is defined as a "(...) temporary localisation, consisting of the interplay of flows of money, visual impressions, verbal and bodily communication." (Hill et al., 2021, p. 645). Locations can be transformed into places through the interactions between people and with the digital and physical environment (Hill et al., 2021). 'Entrepreneurial placemaking' then denotes successful financial, physical, social and digital interactions, (Hill, et al., 2021, p. 645).

This research investigated bottom-up solutions developed by designers / artists, in England and Scotland that address the above outlined business challenges in rural areas. These solutions facilitate peer support and enable creating temporary entrepreneurial places for designers/makers to thrive. Data gathering methods included (see Hill, 2024a for more detail)

- 46 semi-structured interviews (with designers/artists, business support providers, experts, mentors, and facilitators) and a focus group,
- nine days of observations in England and Scotland, and
- informal document gathering and photographs.

Figure 1 Map of creative microclusters identified in 2019, based on webscraped data collected from creative firm websites, based on local authority districts in England. Each colour indicates a distinct cluster. Source: Velez-Ospina et al., 2023, p. 914.

Discussion of key findings

This research findings could illustrate the value of peer support for artist development ([Hill, 2024a](#)). These three networks were investigated, supported by the 2023 RAKE / ISBE fund :

- (1) A physical site with studios and open workspaces for emerging designers/makers was the most engaged network with all stakeholders engaging regularly in peer support. Network 1 formally facilitated exchanges in three ways (a monthly lunch tenant meeting, a WhatsApp group and quarterly site related meetings of all tenants). The site, buildings and

facilities (kitchen, seating area, machine room that can be booked) also facilitate focusing on the physical presence of tenants on the site. Tenants are carefully selected and integrated into the ongoing activities. Participating in the network is facilitated through paying fees for renting a workspace. Two experienced professionals offer business and technical support as part of their job. Additionally, once per year, most network members participate in Open Days for a weekend.

- (2) Network 2 operates mainly online, offering a closed curated platform, for which members pay a monthly membership fee. They gain unlimited business support 1-2-1 and access to business training by business support professionals, who do not solely work for the network, but also have other roles for the managing organisation. Monthly meetings are offered online, combined with regular updates on local and regional exhibitions. Peer support unfolds in these monthly meetings and outside of them, in dedicated online spaces, and in-person for those physically located close to each other. In-person workshops are offered three to four-times a year, and in 2024, for the first time physical exhibitions were organised most of the members participated in.
- (3) Network three, led by an artist, consists of 85 % visual artists meeting weekly for a whole day. The modest monthly fee covers the organiser's bills and expenses and finances the fortnightly experienced artists. These artists offer skills training and feedback for the artistic work. My observations showed me how members share experiences with business relevance, while working alongside each other, from working with galleries to applying for exhibitions. The daily lunch, when participants consume their own food, is significant for further social exchanges and peer discussions as a whole group. The annual exhibition on the peer support leader's premises is advertised through local Facebook groups and other cost-free channels and is the highlight of the year. For some artists, it is the only way they sell to the public.

My stakeholder and expert interviews found that many councillors and private sector / social enterprise staff might struggle to learn about their local artists that do not have public visibility through studios. One artist explained how her role as parent has given her access to lots of opportunities and contacts. Schools, for example, often have collaborations with local artists and could signpost to some local artists, if permission given, to help Councillors develop more relationships. Similarly, my research in a village found that local community centres and churches offer craft workshops run by local artists that are publicly advertised, which are a starting point to find out about local artists and networks.

The engagement in local Facebook groups during a research project in a village in England demonstrated how much this channel is used and still current. The CEO of a local arts focused social enterprise pointed out to me how many walls she sees in Council buildings that are not well equipped with art, and most often this art is not from local artists if there are any exhibits.

Policy and practice recommendations

Policymakers, civil servants and councillors, can serve the local community best in facilitating collaborations between all stakeholders that can support local designers / makers. Those living in remote rural areas, be that in coastal areas or mountains, need mobile offers from banks and business support services, as they cannot rely on consistent internet connectivity.

Policymakers can fund network building amongst, for and by local designers/ artists with small amounts that can have a great impact – on developing technical and business skills as outlined in the findings section (see [Hill, 2024b](#) for details on how to develop a designers/artists' network).

Civil servants can use existing Council communication channels to residents to act as part of the designers/artists' public relations to:

- Make local artists / designers more visible with featuring an artist / designer of the month on the website;
- Add an event/cultural page featuring local exhibitions and artists to increase their market reach.

Local parish and/or district councillors could without cost to the Council:

- Facilitate to offer council buildings frequented by residents and visitors for local craft and art exhibitions and provide room hire at lower fees when rooms are not used anyway (evenings, weekends).
- Act as patrons and/or serve on boards of social enterprises / charities supporting 'the arts' to signify the importance of the role of creative firms for the local economy and communities. Their engagement also signifies to potential funders that the organisation is worth funding.

Practice recommendations

Managers in community centres, tourist sites, heritage sites, creative hubs are in a unique position to facilitate exhibitions of creative goods from local designers/makers to increase their visibility. These exhibitions can become a constant feature in communities celebrating the works of local talent on a regular basis, changing exhibition goods every six to eight weeks. Several artists can showcase their work, attracting more visitors, for example, combining visual arts with ceramics.

Private sector banks can be invited to come to the local area in their 'bank vans'. I visited such a van from one of the large UK banks in a village and saw how grateful residents were using the offers: deposit cash, to take cash away, as there is no local cash machine, gain financial advice in-person. The bank van comes to this village twice per week during lunch time hours.

Private sector and social enterprise run facilities (e.g. tourist sites, cultural heritage sites) can offer support in-kind through providing their walls for exhibitions for local artists / makers and

advertise these exhibitions through the existing newsletter without much additional effort. This engagement shows local embeddedness, valued by many visitors.

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